

THE STUDY OF IMPERFECT COMPLEXES. PART I. CALORIMETRIC STUDY OF COMPLEXES BY JOB'S METHOD OF CONTINUED VARIATION

BY SUSHIL KUMAR SIDDHANTA

Job's method of continued variation has been applied by several workers for the determination of the composition and the dissociation constant of complexes of low stability from a study of properties like extinction coefficient, conductivity, refractivity, etc. In the present work, it has been shown that the molar heat content can be utilised as a property, the variation of which may be employed for the same purpose.

Thermometric titrations were first introduced by Dutoit (*J. chim. phys.*, 1921, 19, 324) to determine the composition of new compound or compounds formed in solution by mixing solutions of two compounds. In this method the temperature change observed on adding gradually the solution of one compound to a definite volume of that of another was plotted against the volume of the first solution added, and the compositions of the new compounds formed in solution were taken to be indicated by the inflexion points. Such a simple method, in the opinion of the present author, is apt to give in many cases inaccurate information as to the composition of the new substance or substances formed. A detailed discussion on this point will be given in Part III of this series.

Titration, using certain molecular properties, such as conductivity, as a guide for the determination of reacting proportions are also in use for a long time. Such a method also, it may be remarked, gives a sharp inflexion point only when a perfect complex is formed and is apt to give inaccurate information about imperfect complexes having large dissociation constant (vide Part III of the series).

Job's method of continued variation for the study of imperfect complexes (Job, *Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 928; *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, x, 9, 113) using an additive molecular property as guide is, however, more reliable in cases where only one complex is formed by mixing two solutions. The method gives not only the composition of the complex formed, but its approximate dissociation constant in addition. In the following reaction between two molecules A and B,

if $(1-x)$ c.c. of a solution of A of molar concentration c per c.c. be added to x c.c. of a solution of B of molar concentration c' per c.c. ($c' = pc$), and if C_1 , C_2 , C_3 be the respective molar concentrations per c.c. of A, B, and A_mB_n after the equilibrium has been attained, the following equations apply for any such mixture.

$$C_1^m \cdot C_2^n = K \cdot C_3 \quad \dots \text{ (A)}$$

where K is the dissociation constant of the complex.

$$C_1 + mC_3 = c(1-x) \quad \dots \text{ (B)}$$

$$C_2 + nC_3 = pcx \quad \dots \text{ (C)}$$

Starting from relations (A), (B), (C) Job showed that equation (1) is true only for that value of x for which C_3 is maximum.

$$\frac{c^{m+n-1} \cdot p^{n-1} \{ (pm+n)x - n \}^{m+n}}{m^{n-1} \cdot n^{m-1}} = K \cdot \{ n - (m+n)x \} (p-1)^{m+n-1} \quad \dots (1)$$

when $p = 1$ (i.e., for equimolecular parent solutions), the right hand side of equation (1) is zero and therefore

$$m/n = 1 - x/x \quad \dots (2)$$

as c, p, m and n are finite constants.

Hence, from a knowledge of the value of x where C_3 is maximum, the formula of the complex can be determined from the ratio m/n using equation (2), taking simplest integral values of m and n provided that the two primary solutions used are of equimolecular concentration. After determining thus the values of m and n , the value of K can be determined by equation (1) using the value of x for maximum C_3 in the case of two primary solutions which are not equimolecular (i.e., where $p \neq 1$).

The problem then obviously reduces to the determination of the value of x for which the concentration C_3 of the complex A_mB_n is maximum, using both equimolecular and non-equimolecular primary solutions of A and B. This offers no special difficulty when A_mB_n has a property not possessed by A and B; then the value of x , where this property is maximum, gives the maximum value of the concentration C_3 of the complex A_mB_n . Usually, however, such a property is difficult to be found. In such cases, Job proposed to study as a function of x any molecular property which obeys the mixture law in the following way:

$$P_{\text{mixture}} = \alpha P_A + \beta P_B + \gamma P_C + \dots$$

where $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \dots$ are the number of moles of A, B, C, ... present in the solution and P_A, P_B, P_C, \dots are the respective molar values of the property P for A, B, C, ...

Job has mathematically showed that the difference, Y , of the observed value of the property P for any mixture of x c.c. of a solution of B and $(1-x)$ c.c. of a solution of A from that calculated for the mixture by the additivity rule with the assumption that no reaction takes place when plotted against the different corresponding values of x , gives a curve, the maximum (or minimum) point of which represents the value of x where C_3 is maximum.

Job (*loc. cit.*) chose molar extinction coefficient as the property to be studied and he determined it spectrophotometrically for various solutions of pure A and B and their mixtures in order to find out the value of Y for different values of x . The same property has been used by Vorsburgh and co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437; 1942, **64**, 1630) to determine the composition of a number of imperfect complexes; these workers also modified Job's method to the study of composition in a few cases, where more than one complexes are formed in solution.

Spacu and Popper (*Bull. Soc. Stiinte, Cluj*, 1934, **7**, 400; 1934, **8**, 5) have used molar refractivity as an indicative property to be studied by Job's method. Molar conductivity has also been used by a number of workers as a guide for the study of complex compounds in solution by Job's method (Dutt, paper communicated to Indian

Chemical Society; Purkayastha and Sen-Sarma, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **23**, 31; Purkayastha, *ibid.*, 1947, **24**, 257; 1948, **25**, 81; Biswas, *ibid.*, 1947, **24**, 345). Biswas (*loc. cit.*) has also studied as a function of the composition of the mixture, the difference of the observed H^+ ion concentration of the mixture from that calculated by additivity rule with the assumption of no reaction taking place in order to determine the composition of the complex formed in solution between molybdic and tartaric acids.

In the present paper, it is proposed that molar heat content is a suitable property to be studied in Job's method of continued variation, so that the deviation Y from the additivity rule is given by the heat of reaction ($-\Delta H$). But since the reaction is to be studied in solution, the heats of solution of the reactants and of the resultant should be considered.

Thus, the heat content of $(1-x)$ c.c. of a solution of A at concentration c

$$= (1-x) \left\{ c \cdot H_A + c q_A + \frac{1}{18} H_{H_2O} \right\}$$

and the heat content of x c.c. of a solution of B at concentration p

$$= x \left\{ p c \cdot H_B + p c q_B + \frac{1}{18} H_{H_2O} \right\}$$

where H_A , H_B and H_{H_2O} are the respective molar heat contents of A, B and H_2O and $c q_A$ and $p c q_B$ are the respective heats of solution of c mols. of A and $p c$ mols. of B, both in 1 c.c. of water, supposing however, that no change of volume takes place on dissolution of solutes and that 1 c.c. of any solution contains $\frac{1}{18}$ mols. of H_2O .

The sum of the heat contents of the two parent solutions before mixing is therefore given by

$$H_{\text{reactants}} = (1-x) \left\{ c \cdot H_A + c q_A \right\} + x \left\{ p c \cdot H_B + p c q_B \right\} + \frac{1}{18} H_{H_2O}$$

By mixing the two parent solutions, we get 1 c.c. of the mixture which after attainment of equilibrium contains C_1 mols. of A, C_2 mols. of B and C_3 mols. of $A_m B_n$. Proceeding as above with the use of analogous notation, and supposing that there is no volume change on mixing the two solutions and that 1 c.c. of any solution contains $\frac{1}{18}$ mols. of H_2O , we can calculate $H_{\text{resultant}}$ of 1 c.c. of this mixture.

$$H_{\text{resultant}} = C_1 \cdot H_A + C_1 q_A + C_2 \cdot H_B + C_2 q_B + C_3 \cdot H_{A_m B_n} + C_3 q_{A_m B_n} + \frac{1}{18} H_{H_2O}$$

The heat of reaction is therefore given by

$$\begin{aligned} (-\Delta H) &= H_{\text{reactants}} - H_{\text{resultant}} \\ &= (1-x) \{ c \cdot H_A + c q_A \} + x \{ p c \cdot H_B + p c q_B \} - \{ C_1 \cdot H_A + C_1 q_A + C_2 \cdot H_B + C_2 q_B \\ &\quad + C_3 \cdot H_{A_m B_n} + C_3 q_{A_m B_n} \} \dots (3) \end{aligned}$$

Now, by the law of partial molal quantities,

${}_c q_A$ = heat of solution of c mols. of A in ν c.c. of water

$$= c \cdot {}_c \bar{q}_A + \frac{\nu}{18} {}_c \bar{q}_{(H_2O)A} \quad \dots (4)$$

where ${}_c \bar{q}_A$ is the differential heat of solution A at concentration c , i.e., heat change due to dissolution of ν mol. of A in a large volume of a solution of A at concentration c and ${}_c \bar{q}_{(H_2O)A}$ is the differential heat of dilution for a solution of A at concentration c i.e., heat change due to the addition of ν mol. of H_2O in a large volume of a solution of A at concentration c .

If the solutions used be moderately dilute so that the heat change due to addition of further amount of water may be neglected, we may neglect the quantity ${}_c \bar{q}_{(H_2O)A}$ in equation (4). Also ${}_c \bar{q}_A$ is practically equal to ${}_0 \bar{q}_A$, the heat of solution of ν mol. of A in a large volume of pure water (instead of in a solution of A at concentration c).

Hence equation (4) can be written as

$${}_c q_A = c \cdot {}_0 \bar{q}_A.$$

Proceeding similarly and using analogous notations, we may have ... (4a)

$${}_p c q_B = p c \cdot {}_0 \bar{q}_B \quad \dots (4b)$$

$${}_c q_A = C_1 \cdot {}_0 \bar{q}_A \quad \dots (4c)$$

$${}_c q_B = C_2 \cdot {}_0 \bar{q}_B \quad \dots (4d)$$

$${}_c q_{AmBn} = C_3 \cdot {}_0 \bar{q}_{AmBn} \quad \dots (4e)$$

Putting (4a, b, c, d, e) in (3) we have

$$(-\Delta H) = (1-x) c \left\{ H_A + {}_0 \bar{q}_A \right\} + x p c \left\{ H_B + {}_0 \bar{q}_B \right\} - \left[C_1 \left\{ H_A + {}_0 \bar{q}_A \right\} + C_2 \left\{ H_B + {}_0 \bar{q}_B \right\} + C_3 \left\{ H_{AmBn} + {}_0 \bar{q}_{AmBn} \right\} \right] \quad \dots (3a)$$

Writing C_1 and C_2 in equation (3a) in terms of C_3 using equations (B) and (C), we have

$$(-\Delta H) = m C_3 \left\{ H_A + {}_0 \bar{q}_A \right\} + n C_3 \left\{ H_B + {}_0 \bar{q}_B \right\} - C_3 \left\{ H_{AmBn} + {}_0 \bar{q}_{AmBn} \right\} \quad \dots (3b)$$

Since $H_A, H_B, H_{AmBn}, {}_0 \bar{q}_A, {}_0 \bar{q}_B, {}_0 \bar{q}_{AmBn}$ are constants we have by differentiating (3b) with respect to x ,

$$\frac{d(-\Delta H)}{dx} = \frac{dC_3}{dx} \left[m \left\{ H_A + {}_0 \bar{q}_A \right\} + n \left\{ H_B + {}_0 \bar{q}_B \right\} - \left\{ H_{AmBn} + {}_0 \bar{q}_{AmBn} \right\} \right] \quad \dots (5)$$

From equation (5) we have

$$\frac{d(-\Delta H)}{dx} = 0, \text{ when } \frac{dC_3}{dx} = 0$$

i. e., $(-\Delta H)$ must be at a maximum or a minimum for that value of x for which C_2 is maximum.

The heat of reaction $(-\Delta H)$ due to mixing x c. c. of a solution of ammonia with $(100-x)$ c. c. of a solution of copper sulphate at equimolecular and non-equimolecular concentrations has been studied by Siddhanta and Guha (details will appear in Part III of this series). It has been shown that for equimolecular solutions the value of x , where $(-\Delta H)$ is maximum, lies at 80 c. c. So that $m/n=1:4$ by equation (2) *i. e.*, complex ion formed is $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]^{++}$; also using non-equimolecular solutions the values of x , where $(-\Delta H)$ is maximum, have been utilised to calculate K , the dissociation constant of this complex, by applying equation (1). The value of K obtained in this way accords fairly well with that obtained by Job from the study of molar extinction coefficients by the method of continued variation. The special advantage of this process discussed above is that it directly gives the difference Y (*i. e.*, $-\Delta H$) from the additivity rule for any mixture by one reading only. But if any other property be chosen to be studied, three readings of the property will be necessary to find out Y for any mixture—two readings for the two parent solutions and the third for the mixture. The process, introduced here, is therefore more direct and takes much shorter time in comparison with any other prevalent process of study by Job's method of continued variation. Another remarkable feature of the process is that it gives the value of both K and $(-\Delta H)$ and hence the approximate value of the free energy change $(-\Delta F)$ and the entropy change $(-\Delta S)$ of the complex formation can be calculated by the well known relations

$$(-\Delta F) = RT \ln K$$

$$(-\Delta H) = (-\Delta F) + T(-\Delta S).$$

There is, however, one serious limitation to the process that should be mentioned here. If the heat of dilution of the parent solutions used be not negligible in comparison with the heat of formation of the complex, the process will fail to yield good results. In the author's estimate, the process is workable if the heats of dilution of the parent solutions used do not exceed 10% of the value of the heat of formation of the complex.

The author's grateful thanks are due to Prof. P. Rây. Palit Professor of Chemistry, Calcutta University for his kind guidance and interest. Thanks are also due to Prof. N. K. Sen, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Presidency College, Calcutta, for taking interest and offering facilities.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

Received July 9, 1948.